

where, the coordinated water molecules have been omitted for the sake of simplicity. From equilibrium (1), we obtain,

$$[\text{C}_1] = K_1 [\text{Ru}^{III}] [\text{OH}^-] \quad (2)$$

The ruthenium(III)-catalysed oxidation of alcohols^{11,12}, amines¹³ and primary aminoalcohols¹ have shown to proceed via an intermediate complex C₁ and the substrate. On the basis of above facts and the experimental results, the mechanism for ruthenium(III)-catalysed oxidation of diethanolamine may be represented as

The rate of disappearance of Fe(CN)₆³⁻ for catalysed path is given by equation (6),

$$-\frac{d}{dt} [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}] =$$

$$2K_1 K_3 K_4 k_5 [\text{S}] [\text{OH}^-] [\text{Ru}^{III}] [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]^2 \quad (6)$$

where, $K_3 = k_3/k_{-3}$ and $K_4 = k_4/k_{-4}$.

At higher hexacyanoferrate(III) concentrations, reaction becomes complicated. Thus at lower hexacyanoferrate(III) concentration, according to above rate law equation (6), the reaction is first order in each substrate, alkali and ruthenium(III), and second order in hexacyanoferrate(III). The results are in agreement with rate law equation (6).

The plot of k_{obs} vs [Ru^{III}] gave intercept suggesting that rate of uncatalysed path is not negligible. The value of intercept could not be compared directly with rate of uncatalysed reaction reported⁴, since the uncatalysed reaction follows different kinetics, being first order in oxidant in contrast to second order dependence of rate in ruthenium(III) catalysed reaction. In this proposed mechanism for catalysed path, the steps responsible for uncatalysed reaction have also not been included, therefore, the intercept is also not reflected by rate law equation (6).

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Solvent Steric Effect and its Correlation with a Function of Solvent Mass

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It has been suggested¹ that the rate-retardation observed for the solvolysis of tert-butyl halides on changing the solvent through methanol, ethanol, isopropanol and tert-butanol (sterically, α-series) is likely to be due to increasing steric hindrance to solvation of the carbonium ion (or ion-pair) by the increasing bulk of the solvent molecule. In the present work, this 'solvent steric effect' is further demonstrated for a set of alcohols of normal series. Moreover, a correlation between the solvent steric effect and a function of solvent molecular weight, giving good correlation coefficients, is reported.

Experimental

The first order rate constants of the solvolyses of tert-butyl chloride were determined in n-pentanol, n-butanol, n-pentanol, n-hexanol and n-heptanol at 50°. For purification of the solvents and for determining the rate constants, methods described in literature were followed^{2,3}.

Results and Discussion

The results and all the pertinent data are given in Table 1.

The solvolysis rate is found to decrease with increasing number of methylene groups in the

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TABLE 1—DATA SHOWING CORRELATION BETWEEN RATE/EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANTS AND REDUCED MOLECULAR WEIGHTS OF SUBSTRATES AND SOLVENT ALCOHOLS

Alcohol	$k \times 10^7$	$\log_{10} k + 7$	$\log_{10}(1/\mu)$	Correlation coefficient	Slope	Energy of activation kcal
Solvolysis of tert-butyl chloride ^a						
(i) Normal series						
Ethanol	46.04 ^a	1.663 0	0.512 1	0.998	4.69	—
p-Propanol	22.36	1.350 0	0.438 3			—
n-Butanol	10.59	1.025 0	0.385 4			25.80
n-Pentanol	7.534	0.877 0	0.345 3			24.80
n-Hexanol	5.521	0.742 0	0.313 6			25.04
n-Heptanol	4.539	0.657 0	0.281			24.28
(ii) α -Series ^a						
Methanol	425.5	2.629 0	0.617 1	1.00	9.31	31.08
Ethanol	46.04	1.663 0	0.512 1			30.86
iso-Propanol	8.464	0.927 6	0.438 3			30.32
tert-Butanol	3.343	0.524 1	0.385 4			31.68
Keto-enol equilibria of ethylacetoacetate:						
Normal series	% Enol ^b	$\log_{10} K$				
Ethanol	10.52	0.929 7	0.468 8	0.989	1.00	
n-Propanol	12.45	0.847 0	0.386 7			
n-Butanol	15.33	0.742 2	0.280 0			

^aRef. 1. ^bRef. 6.

alcohol molecule for the alcohols of normal series, as was found¹ for those of α -series. The normal alcohols have the same polarity, their dipole moments having very nearly the same value ($\mu = 1.54 - 1.67$ D)⁴. Therefore, by the same arguments as in reference 1, 'solvent steric effect' on solvation must be the cause of retardation.

The lesser magnitude of retardation in the normal alcohols can be attributed to the difference in the mode of substitution—the bulk increase at the reaction centre being less for normal alcohol series than for α -series*.

With regard to the keto-enol equilibrium (Table 1), the enol is expected to be less solvated than the ketone due to intramolecular hydrogen bonding⁵. Therefore, with increasing steric hindrance to solvation more of the ketone is expected to be converted to enol, and this has been observed.

Next, a good linear correlation is observed for both the series of solvents, between the logarithms of the first order solvolysis rate constants and the logarithms of $(1/\mu)$ of the reaction

systems where μ is the reduced molecular weight of the substrate and the solvent, given by $\mu = (M_A M_B)/(M_A + M_B)$, A and B representing the substrate and the solvent respectively and M_A and M_B , their molecular weights. The correlation is also obtained between the logarithm of the keto-enol equilibrium constant and $\log(1/\mu)$ in normal alcohol series.

It may be pointed out that whereas parameters such as Y -value, dielectric constant *etc.* compare the solvents on their bulk properties of solvation ion-stabilisation *etc.*, the correlation between rate/equilibrium constants and the reduced molecular weights shown here represents a relationship between a specific effect (steric) by, and a basic characteristic (mol. wt) of the solvent.

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*A comparison of the steric effects of the two series is possible as the polarities of all the involved alcohols are very nearly the same ($\mu = 1.54 - 1.81$ D)⁴.